

One-pot synthesis of substituted steroidal thiazoles

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Substituted steroidal thiazoles (4-9) have been synthesized from some 5 α -hydroxy-6-ketosteroids (1-3) by the reaction with NBS, thiourea/thioacetamide and benzoyl peroxide as catalyst.

Thiazoles have been reported to possess considerable pharmacological potentialities¹. In continuation of our earlier studies², we report herein the synthesis of some steroidal thiazoles (4-9).

3 β ,5-Dihydroxy-5 α -cholestan-6-one (1)³, its 3 β -acetoxy (2)³ and 3 β -chloro (3)⁴ analogs on treatment with NBS, thiourea/thioacetamide and benzoyl peroxide as a catalyst in benzene furnished 4-9.

1-3	
	R
1	OH
2	OAc
3	Cl

4-9		
	R	R'
4	OH	NH ₂
5	OAc	NH ₂
6	Cl	NH ₂
7	OH	CH ₃
8	OAc	CH ₃
9	Cl	CH ₃

Reaction of 3 β ,5-dihydroxy-5 α -cholestan-6-one (1) with NBS and thiourea. General procedure : A mixture of 1 (1.0 g, 2.39 mmol), NBS (0.5 g, 2.39 mmol), thiourea (0.179 g, 2.39 mmol) and benzoyl peroxide (catalytic amount) in benzene (40 ml) was refluxed for 8 h. The solvent was then distilled off under reduced pressure and the residue treated with crushed ice and extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with water, K₂CO₃ solution (5%) and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. Evaporation of the solvent gave an oil which was chromatographed over silica gel (20 g) column. Elution with a mixture of light petroleum ether : ether (5 : 1) gave 3 β ,5-dihydroxy-2'-amino-5 α -cholest-6-eno[6,7-*d*]thiazole (4) as semi-solid (72.3%) (Found : C, 70.9; H, 9.8; N, 5.9. C₂₈H₄₆N₂O₂S requires :

C, 70.84; H, 9.76; N, 5.9%); ν_{\max} (nujol) 3400 (OH), 3255, 3160 (NH₂), 1630 (C=C), 1520 (C=N), 1455, 1375 (C-N), 660 cm⁻¹ (C-S); δ (CDCl₃) 4.75 (2H, s, NH₂, exchangeable with D₂O), 4.48 (1H, m, $W_{1/2}$ 17 Hz, C3 α -H), 3.35 (2H, br s, exchangeable with D₂O, 2 \times OH), 1.2, 0.72, 0.91 and 0.81 (5 \times CH₃); m/z 474 (M⁺), 459 (M-CH₃), 456 (M-H₂O), 361 (M-C₈H₁₇). Ketones 2 and 3 provided thiazoles 5 and 6 respectively, under identical reaction conditions : 5 (62.5%), m.p. 205° (Found : C, 69.8; H, 9.4; N, 5.4. C₃₀H₄₈N₂O₃S requires : C, 69.72; H, 9.36; N, 5.42%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3400 (OH), 3300, 3150 (NH₂), 1730, 1265 (OCOCH₃), 1630 (C=C), 1525 (C=N), 1460, 1375 (C-N), 660 cm⁻¹ (C-S); δ (CDCl₃) 5.01 (1H, br m, $W_{1/2}$ 18 Hz, C3 α -H), 4.92 (2H, br s, exchangeable with deuterium, NH₂), 3.42 (1H, br s, exchangeable with D₂O, C5 α -OH), 2.05 (3H, s, OCOCH₃), 1.2 -0.7 (angular and side-chain methyl protons); m/z 516 (M⁺), 501 (M-CH₃), 498 (M-H₂O), 430 (M-AcOH), 403 (M-C₈H₁₇); 6, oil (61.5%) (Found : C, 68.2; H, 9.2; N, 5.7. C₂₈H₄₅N₂O₂OSCl requires : C, 68.19; H, 9.19; N, 5.68%); ν_{\max} (neat) 3430 (OH), 3300, 3150 (NH₂), 1638 (C=C), 1530 (C=N), 1470, 1380 (C-N), 780 (C-Cl), 655 cm⁻¹ (C-S); δ (CDCl₃) 4.71 (2H, br s, exchangeable with D₂O, NH₂), 3.41 (1H, br s, exchangeable with D₂O, C5 α -OH), 4.03 (1H, m, $W_{1/2}$ 17 Hz, C3 α -H), 1.2-0.75 (angular and side-chain methyl protons); m/z 492/494 (M⁺), 477/479 (M-CH₃), 474/476 (M-H₂O), 456 (M-HCl).

Reaction of 3 β ,5-dihydroxy-5 α -cholestan-6-one (1) with NBS and thioacetamide. General procedure : A mixture of 1 (1.0 g, 2.39 mmol) and NBS (0.5 g, 2.39 mmol) was refluxed with thioacetamide (0.179 g, 2.39 mmol) and benzoyl peroxide (catalytic amount) in benzene (40 ml) for 6 h. After usual work up (as described in previous reaction) and evaporation of the solvent gave an oil which was chromatographed over silica gel (20 g) column and elution with petroleum ether : ether (10 : 1) afforded 3 β ,5-dihydroxy-2'-methyl-5 α -cholest-6-eno[6,7-*d*]thiazole as an oil (7; 62.5%) (Found : C, 73.5; H, 10.0; N, 2.9. C₂₉H₄₇N₂O₂S requires : C, 73.52; H, 9.99; N, 2.95%); ν_{\max} (neat) 3400

Note

(OH), 1630 (C=C), 1530 (C=N), 1470, 1380 (C-N), 655 cm^{-1} (C-S); δ (CDCl_3) 4.48 (1H, m, $W_{1/2}$ 18 Hz, C3 α -H), 3.21 (2H, s, C5 α -OH, C3 β -OH exchangeable with D_2O), 2.51 (3H, s, -N=C-CH₃), 1.2, 0.75, 0.9 and 0.8 (5 \times CH₃); m/z 473 (M^+), 458 (M-CH₃), 455 (M-H₂O), 360 (M-C₈H₁₇). Ketones 2 and 3 under similar reaction conditions afford thiazoles 8 and 9, respectively : 8 (46.5%), m.p. 178° (Found : C, 72.2; H, 9.6; N, 2.7. C₃₁H₄₉NO₃S requires : C, 72.19; H, 9.57; N, 2.71%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3400 (OH), 1735, 1240 (CH₃COO), 1625 (C=C), 1530 (C=N), 1470, 1385 (C-N), 665 cm^{-1} (C-S); δ (CDCl_3) 5.01 (1H, br m, $W_{1/2}$ 18 Hz, C3 α -H), 3.41 (1H, s, C5 α -OH, exchangeable with D_2O), 2.53 (3H, s, N=C-CH₃), 1.96 (3H, s, CH₃COO), 1.25–0.75 (angular and side-chain methyl protons); m/z 515 (M^+), 500 (M-CH₃), 497 (M-H₂O), 455 (M-AcOH), 402 (M-C₈H₁₇); 9, oil (58.5%) (Found : C, 70.7; H, 9.4; N, 2.8. C₂₉H₄₆NOSCl requires : C, 70.76; H, 9.42; N, 2.84%); ν_{max} (neat) 3450 (OH), 1620 (C=C), 1535 (C=N), 1465, 1385 (C-Cl), 655 cm^{-1} (C-S); δ (CDCl_3) 3.85 (1H, br m, $W_{1/2}$ 17 Hz, C3 α -H), 3.41 (1H, s, C5 α -OH, exchangeable with D_2O), 2.53 (3H, s, N=C-CH₃), 1.23–0.76 (angular and side-chain methyl protons); m/z 491/493 (M^+), 476/478 (M-CH₃), 473/475 (M-H₂O), 455 (M-HCl), 378/380 (M-C₈H₁₇).

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